

Grant Agreement N° 101147457

INERRANT

Deliverable D8.2 Management Guide

Contractual delivery date:
M06

Actual delivery date:
31.10.2024

Responsible partner:
P11: EURICE, Germany

Project Title	INERRANT – Integrating Novel matERials with scalable processes for safer and recyclAble Li-ion baTteries
Deliverable number	D8.2
Related Task	T8.1 - Implementation of efficient management and support structures
Author(s):	EURICE
Type¹	R
Distribution level²	PU

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

Work package number	WP08 - Project Management and Scientific Coordination
Work package leader	P01 – FORTH
Abstract:	The management guide includes a description of the consortium's structures and operations, risk management, and details of best practices for dissemination and communication activities.
Keyword List:	Roles, communication workflows, quality management, risk management, Organisation, best practices

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement no 101147457. This report reflects the views only of the authors and does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible or liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

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Document Description

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	26/08/2024	Introduction of content	Sam Hoefman (EURICE)
V0.2	31/08/2024	Internal review and validation by COO	FORTH
V0.3	23.10.2024	Modification due to the public nature of the deliverable	Heiko Poth, Janine Jost (EURICE)

Executive Summary

This Management Guide lays down standard workflows and processes for the most common and recurring management activities on the INERRANT consortium level. In addition, it will give guidelines and recommendations with regard to communication within the project and dissemination of project results. The guide is made available to all INERRANT partners to foster active collaboration and a smooth implementation from the start.

The project activities are implemented in line with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27th April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

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Terms and abbreviations

Abbreviations	Definitions
CA	Consortium Agreement
COO	Coordinator
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
LIBs	Lithion-ION Batteries
MT	Management Team
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
SC	Steering Committee
TL (R)	Team Leader (Report)
WPL (R)	Work Package Leader (Report)

1. Introduction

This Management Guide is prepared within the scope of WP8 “Project management and scientific coordination”. Establishing roles and workflows at the beginning of a project is crucial for the project’s successful implementation, particularly in such an ambitious project as INERRANT. It gives all consortium partners a sound work basis when they know the correct contact persons and follow certain standard procedures. Professional project management also includes a close monitoring of processes and achievement of deadlines and milestones, as well as a regular risk assessment and quality control.

This Management Guide gives guidelines and clear recommendations to the consortium partners with regard to a number of standard managing processes and workflows in INERRANT. This helps to enhance the quality of project outcomes and minimize risks as they can be detected at an early stage. **Due to the public nature of this deliverable, internal processes and procedures are described in a simplistic manner in this document. A more detailed description is available to the consortium internally.**

Certain roles and procedures are already defined in the Description of Action (DoA). This document is a supplement to the DoA and gives a concise overview of those roles and procedures already defined, while also establishing additional workflows that are necessary for the project’s proper implementation.

2. Quality assurance

Quality assurance will be the underlying principle for all of the conducted work, as well as the defined workflows and assigned roles in INERRANT.

Ensuring quality in INERRANT means that it is set on **three pillars**.

- **Pillar 1: Definition of roles, assignment of tasks and establishment of communication flows**

In INERRANT a number of roles and functions have been defined. Specific tasks have been attributed to these roles and specific contact persons have been assigned.

This process ensures that the tasks of all such roles are clear and everybody in the consortium knows the contact person that is in charge.

Consequently, the consortium partners will receive reliable answers when addressing the correct persons. This will help them to perform their work correctly.

Pillar 2: Establishing workflows

Workflows for standard procedures have been defined in INERRANT. This includes:

- Reporting
 - Meeting organisation
 - Preparation of Deliverables
 - Monitoring of milestones
 - Risk assessment
- **Pillar 3: Establishing internal reviewing processes**

In addition to the two pillars mentioned above, internal reviewing processes have been established at several levels in the project implementation to ensure quality:

- For preparing deliverables
- At Steering Committee (SC) meetings (every eight weeks)
- At General Assembly (GA) meetings (once a year, more if required)

3. Roles, assigned tasks and related communication workflows

Several roles and positions as well as workflows have been defined in INERRANT to guarantee the smooth implementation of the project. In the following, more detailed information is provided.

3.1 INERRANT Boards

3.1.1 INERRANT Project Management Team (PMT)

The INERRANT Project Management Team (PMT) consists of the coordinator, assisted by EURICE.

Table 1 INERRANT Project Management Team

Partner	Representative
FORTH	Spyros Yannopoulos
FORTH	Magda Spella
EURICE	Sam Hoefman

The technical implementation of the project includes the following tasks:

- Oversee the overall project progress and coordinating the overall workplan
- Monitor compliance of the partners with their obligations
- Continuously review and update the initial risk assessment
- With the Steering Committee (see 3.1.4): control and monitor Work Package status measured against deliverables and milestones in order to ensure the timely and accurate work plan follow-up
- Identify technical organisational problems and troubleshooting

The operational day-to-day management includes the following tasks:

- Administrative and financial support
- Information and advice to partners on administrative, regulative and financial issues
- Control of deliverable timeliness
- Quality and risk management
- Organisation of report preparation, distribution and archiving
- Internal progress report and work plan updates
- Monitoring of overall project progress based on the WPL reports
- Preparation, collection and maintenance of contractual documents
- Quality and consistency check with respect to technical and contractual requirements

There is always a close interaction between the PMT members by e-mail and regular status Teams calls.

3.1.2 Work Package Leaders

Only the partners that lead a work package (WP) according to the DoA appoint a Work Package Leader (WPL) and deputy (if applicable). WPLs assume the role of an **interface between the partners of their respective work package and the COO**. They are responsible for the scientific coordination of their work package, including the coordination of the workflow between their WP and the others and the activities of all partners involved in their WP. They keep the PMT informed about the development, progress, and status of their WP on a regular basis and arrange for the timely submission of deliverables relating to their WP in cooperation with the lead beneficiary of the deliverable.

Concerning periodic and internal reporting, WPLs are **responsible for preparing the WPL report** on the basis of the partner contributions.

Table 2 INERRANT Work Package Leaders

WP	Partner
WP1	FORTH
WP2	UCD
WP3	UJEP
WP4	PLE
WP5	IBG
WP6	VERKOR
WP7	EURICE
WP8	FORTH

3.1.3 INERRANT General Assembly

The INERRANT General Assembly will act as the ultimate democratic decision-making body in INERRANT. It will be composed of one representative per partner chaired by the COO. Decisions will be made by consensus whenever possible; majority voting (one vote per partner, coordinator casting vote), will be implemented. Decisions will comprise any technical or scientific changes to the overall work plan, reallocation of tasks or resources, etc. A detailed Grant Agreement and a Consortium Agreement underpinning the project were concluded and thus only few, if any, substantive disagreements are to be expected. The General Assembly shall be responsible for determining policies and making decisions in relation to the overall management of the Action and the finding of amicable solutions for any unresolved disputes between the Beneficiaries relating to the execution of the Action.

The General Assembly will meet once a year on the occasion of the annual consortium meetings.

3.1.4 Steering Committee

The INERRANT Steering Committee (SC) is made up of all WPLs. The SC shall be responsible of early identification of possible technical and organisational problems and for trouble shooting at the project level, taking into account interrelationships and dependencies of the WPs at large and ensuring a timely and accurate work plan follow-up. The SC will keep the PMT informed of the progress status on a regular basis for the overall execution of the Action, alignment across all WPs, decision making and the initial finding of amicable solutions for any disputes between the Beneficiaries relating to the execution of the Action. It will ensure the smooth operation of the Action and guarantee that all efforts are focused towards the Action Objectives, Deliverables and Project Milestones. This will be achieved

by regular meetings, at least every two months and thorough reviews of progress reports. It will also ensure that all Beneficiaries are regularly updated on the scientific progress.

3.1.5 Communication Committee

The INERRANT Communication Committee has been established and is meeting regularly. The Communication Committee will guide external project communication, content production and quality assurance for communication activities.

3.1.6 Advisory Board (AB)

An Advisory Board (SAB) has already been pre-established during the proposal and Grant Agreement Preparation phase, as the cited members in the DoA have already initiated dialogues with the INERRANT consortium. Their insights will not be confined to the area of LIBs for e-mobility applications but will cover a broader spectrum of aspects relevant to INERRANT. Members of the Advisory Board come from two large industrial companies, two European agencies, a research institute and a large investment firm.

3.2 Communication within the consortium

3.2.1 General rules

The following communication rules are defined in INERRANT with regard to the PMT:

- All communication regarding any issue or problem should be directed to both the COO (via Spyros Yannopoulos and Magda Spella) and the PMO (via Sam HOEFMAN).
- Only the COO (involving the PMO) will communicate with the EC Project Officer (PO) and send documents or information. The partners should not directly contact the PO themselves.

In close cooperation with the COO, the PMO will take on the main communication role with the consortium with regard to the distribution of meeting material, minutes, agenda, information regarding upcoming deliverables and follow-up information about reporting.

INERRANT promotes an open communication policy: all partners are encouraged to discuss openly and raise issues/problems as early as possible.

3.2.2 Contacts list

A list of WPLs, WP members, key contacts and their deputies as well as the institutions' financial, administrative and legal contacts is available to the consortium.

Updates will be made as required and stored in the project management platform.

Each partner is obliged to send changes with regard to their contact persons immediately to the PMT.

3.2.3 Project management platform

A password-protected internal Management Platform has been set up for the project (see D8.1) and will be used as the project management platform to implement the project tasks.

Accounts have been given to the key contacts of all partners and to as many team members as possible. The standard workflows, as mentioned below, will be managed via the platform:

- Project Monitoring = Traffic Light
- Deliverable preparation
- Reporting
- Meeting organisation

Additionally to this, the platform is used to inform all partners about upcoming publications and dissemination activities, thus giving them an easy way to respect the 45-day period of notice stipulated for the dissemination of project results.

A detailed guidance document is available in the management platform and a live webinar is conducted to ensure that all partners know how to use the platform. A recording of this is made available.

3.3 Workflows

3.3.1 Deliverable's workflow

To guarantee the timely submission of deliverables that meet the requirements of the EC and the reviewers with regard to their scientific content and excellence as well as their formal appearance, a workflow together with a deliverables template have been prepared.

A reminder will be sent to the lead beneficiary including the deliverable title, the due date and the workflow as defined by the PMT.

All partners are asked to make their best efforts to ensure that the deliverables are submitted on time.

3.3.2 Delay/Postponement

Definition of terms:

- Delay

A deliverable has not been submitted on time.

This can be the case when no information has been provided that the deliverable needs to be postponed or when the deliverable is submitted a little later than foreseen without proactively informing about a postponement.

- Postponement

A deliverable is actively postponed to a new due date.

This is the case when the Lead Beneficiary lets the PMT know about the delay of a deliverable via the traffic light, either at the time of the reminder or at any earlier point when it becomes clear that the deliverable is delayed and provides a new date for its submission.

Cases of “delay” should be avoided. In INERRANT the consortium prefers a proactive information policy. Information about postponements will proactively be forwarded also to the EC.

When it becomes apparent that a deliverable will not be available on time, the lead beneficiary should inform the PMT and COO immediately about it using the following template.

Table 3 INERRANT Template to explain delay on a deliverable

Deliverable x.x

Explanation/ Reason	
Impact on other tasks	
Impact on resources	
Impact on planning	
Corrective Action/ Contingency	
New due date	

3.3.3 Project internal review process for deliverables

Deliverables are always reviewed and approved by the PMT and the COO. Additionally, internal reviewers were appointed to all deliverables to ensure high technical quality. The Work Package Leaders and those internal reviewers will be informed about an upcoming deliverable together with the Lead Beneficiary (via the Management Platform). When writing the deliverable, the lead beneficiary will make sure to give enough time for the review before submission of the deliverable.

3.3.4 Milestones

It is not required to prepare a report for the achievement of milestones.

As soon as a milestone is achieved, a box will be ticked in the EC's portal and the appropriate date will be given.

The achievement of milestones is monitored via the Project Management Platform similarly to the process for deliverables.

For delays/postponements, the lead beneficiaries are asked to inform the PMT as early as possible.

3.3.5 Meeting organisation

Project progress meetings/General Assembly (GA) meetings will be held at least once a year in INERRANT. The meetings will be organised in a joint effort of the local host, the PMO and the COO. The PMO will strongly support the local host to make the meeting organisation less time-intensive and stressful for them.

In terms of quality assurance as well as risk assessment, the WPLs will prepare presentations detailing the progress of their work and outlining the upcoming tasks and problems that have occurred.

These WP sessions will give the opportunity to discuss the progress and the quality of the work performed among all consortium partners. This will foster good quality of project output.

The WPLs will be asked to keep minutes during their WP presentation and provide them subsequently to the PMT who will compile the overall minutes for the project progress meetings and circulate them in accordance with the Consortium Agreement.

Other meetings

Further meetings, e.g., work group meetings, technical meetings, etc. can be set up any time in person, via telephone conferences, Microsoft Teams or other means of communication.

3.4 Reporting workflow

There will be two kinds of reports in INERRANT:

- Periodic Technical Reports to be submitted to the EC after M18 and M36;
- Internal Progress Reports after M9 and M27

A report needs to be handed in within 60 days after the reporting period's end. For instance, for the 1st Periodic Technical Report, this means 60 days after the end of M18, i.e., October 31st 2025 + 60 days = December 31th, 2025.

3.4.1 Periodic technical reports

Since Periodic Technical Reports are documents to be officially provided to the EC via the EC's portal, they follow a certain structure defined by the EC.

One part of the report will be directly included in the EC's portal; another part will be prepared in a Word template provided by the EC.

Sections directly reported in the portal (Part A):

- Financial statement including explanation
- Project Summary
- Researchers involved in the project
- Critical risks
- Dissemination/Communication activities
- Publications
- Standards
- Patents (IPR)
- Data sets
- Beneficiaries Feedback
- Impact
- Results
- Other Results

Information for these sections (except for financial statements) will be collected by the PMO with dedicated forms/templates.

For the financial statements, the financial contacts will receive a reminder from the PMO to complete and submit their statements in the EC's portal. Information provided will be checked by the PMT and approved by the COO.

Sections included in the Word template (Part B – Technical report):

- Explanation of the work carried out and overview of the progress (Objectives & Explanation of work carried out per WP)
- Impact
- Follow-Up of Recommendations and comments from previous review(s) (if applicable)
- Exploitation primarily in non-associated third countries (if applicable)
- Open Science
- Deviations from Annex I and Annex II (if applicable)

The deadlines including precise dates for the delivery of the individual reports and parts of the report will be communicated by the PMO shortly before the beginning of the reporting (i.e., at the end of the reporting period).

The PMO will provide support in any aspect related to the reporting, including advice for financial reporting.

Templates to collect input from the partners will be made available to facilitate the preparation of the overall report. They follow the structure of the Periodic Technical Reports required by the EC.

3.4.2 Internal Progress Reports

Internal Progress Reports will be prepared in the same way as the Periodic Technical Reports, however, the report will not include all sections required for the Periodic Technical Report as the Internal Progress Report is especially intended to monitor the scientific progress of the project against deliverables, milestones and budget.

Since the EC Portal will not be used for the Internal Progress Reports, a very simple Excel template will be distributed to the financial administrations of the partners to collect an update of their use of resources. They will be asked to fill out the template according to the same basic rules applicable to the financial reporting for Periodic Reports. Estimates will be sufficient.

Deadlines including precise dates for the delivery of the individual parts of the report will be communicated in due time by the PMO via e-mail.

4. Risk management

A thorough risk assessment has already been performed at proposal stage of the project. These risks are considered “foreseen risks. During the project term, the work in the project will be consistently assessed to be able to identify new and unforeseen risks.

The risks have been marked with a clear system marking the level of the risk with colour codes (green = low (L), orange = middle (M), red = high (H)). This is used to visualise the likelihood and severity of occurrence of such risks.

4.1 Regular risk management and assessment procedures

EURICE will facilitate risk management throughout the project and support FORTH. EURICE will maintain a risk register for all risks including unforeseen risks. A regular risk identification will be performed throughout the project at different occasions:

- During the PMT calls
- During the Steering Committee calls
- At the General Assembly meetings
- On the occasion of preparing the Periodic Reports

New and unforeseen risks will be reported by the Work Package Leaders in the meetings and in the report. The risk assessment table (Risk Register) is a living document and viable monitoring tool for the implementation of INERRANT. Within the scope of preparing the annual reports (and ad hoc when deemed necessary), the COO and WPL together with the PMT will update the list of risks with new and unforeseen risks. At the same time, all the risks already reported will be (re)evaluated. Based on this evaluation, the risk level might change after each round of assessment. Appropriate action as indicated in the risk mitigation plan will be taken, if required. The consortium will work closely together to solve issues in a timely manner and in the best interest of the project. FORTH as the project coordinator will ensure proper risk assessment throughout duration of the project, and will lead the development of risk mitigation plans with support from WPLs/all partners.

5. Best Practice

This chapter sums up certain actions which should be taken on a regular basis during the implementation of INERRANT and describes standards that have been defined to guarantee that the project is managed in the best possible manner.

In general, partners of INERRANT are asked to make their best efforts to ensure the timely implementation of the project in a proper and professional manner.

5.1 Information on Dissemination and Communication activities

Communicating and disseminating the project results is an important activity to raise awareness about the project's outcomes and relevance. This is particularly important in INERRANT since it is vital for the project's success that stakeholders such as the industry sector, universities, research institutions etc. are aware of the project as well as the planned activities and its results.

A basic Communication Concept is prepared for INERRANT. It defines target groups, communication channels and dedicated messages. It is accessible to all partners as a basis for their dissemination and communication activities. While this Communication Concept will be prepared centrally by the Communication Committee, the project partners will engage also in individual communication and dissemination activities.

Being aware and knowing what the individual partners are doing to communicate about the project and disseminate the project's output is important to assess dissemination and communication activities and to take timely measures should these activities not be sufficient.

The partners are requested to provide information on all their planned project-related communication and dissemination activities (press releases, presentations at conferences, workshops, organisation of events, media coverage, press releases etc.) once a year in the preparation of the yearly Communication and Dissemination Activity Plan and via the project management tool on a regular basis and in a timely manner.

There is a mandatory 45 days notification period for disseminating results. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted. For presentations, circulating the abstract will, for instance, serve this purpose.

Lastly, with the reporting or for the preparation of dissemination-related deliverables, the partners will be asked to update their activities in a list.

Note: The act of giving a presentation at a conference/workshop is considered a “dissemination activity”. Publishing the presentation in conference proceedings or similar is considered a “publication”. In this case, two entries will have to be made in the Project Management Platform.

5.2 Information on publications

The partners are requested to enter their publications in the project management tool on a regular basis and in a timely manner.

It is mandatory to inform the other project partners 45 days in advance about a planned publication.

The partners are requested to use the project management tool to send an automated publication notice to all partners: they should make an appropriate entry (see manual) and, by selecting all users as “watchers”, the notification will automatically be sent to the project partners.

To avoid inquiries during reporting, the partners are asked to give as much information as possible already when entering the publication. They may update their entry at any time when new information becomes available.

All Open Access publications collected via the project management tool will be entered in the EC’s portal so that they are properly reported to the EC.

Partners will be asked to update their activities in a list for the purpose of monitoring such activities at the latest with the reporting or for the preparation of publication-related deliverables.

5.3 Open Access

Following the EC’s approach of Open Science, in Horizon Europe, all partners are obliged to ensure **Open Access** to

- 1) peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results,
- 2) scientific research data.

5.3.1 Peer-reviewed scientific publications

The partners may publish their peer-reviewed publication in the venue of their choice, which can be:

- a closed (i.e., subscription) venue³,
- an open access publishing venue (e.g., an open access journal or platform); or
- in a hybrid publishing venue, provided that all the Open Access related obligations as detailed in Annex 5 of the GA are complied with.

In addition, they are required to make their publication available by depositing a machine-readable version in a repository providing immediate Open Access.

This means that the publication must be made available at the same time as the first publication:

- Through a trusted repository for scientific publications, and
- Using specific open licenses (a Creative Commons license – CC BY⁴ in most cases – or its equivalent)

As repository the partner can choose an institutional repository (if available), a disciplinary repository (such as Europe PMC) or the repository Zenodo which is an EC-cofounded, multidisciplinary, free repository.

Only publishing in an Open Access journal, i.e., without depositing the publication in a repository, does not comply with the Open Access requirement. All peer-reviewed publications must be deposited in suitable repositories providing Open Access.

Partners are reminded at all times that for all peer-reviewed publications, Open Access is mandatory. It is as well encouraged for all publications that are not peer-reviewed.

Gold open access charges for papers in subscription/hybrid journals are not eligible for funding.

The European Commission has its own Open Access publishing platform Open Research Europe (ORE). It is offered as an additional publishing option to all Horizon Europe beneficiaries. Since ORE deposits all publications automatically in Zenodo, all Open Access requirements are fulfilled when using the publication option via ORE.

A short note also on metadata: Metadata of deposited publications must be

- open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent;
- in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable); and
- provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, their organisations and the grant.

5.3.2 Scientific research data

Under Horizon Europe, the partners are asked to manage responsibly the digital research data generated in the action in line with the FAIR principles. In addition, a Data Management Plan (DMP, D2.1) must be set up at the beginning of the project (and regularly updated). Open Access to research

³ while making the publication immediately available through an OA repository.

⁴ The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited. More information is available [here](#).

data should be ensured via a trusted repository under the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’.

The partner may decide not to provide Open Access to research data, if it goes against his legitimate interests or due to other justified reasons (e.g., confidentiality or security concerns). The reasons not to provide Open Access to certain research data must be explained in the Data Management Plan.

Metadata is also an issue for deposited data. Metadata must be:

- open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded),
- in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable), and
- provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, their organisations and the grant.

5.4 Acknowledgment and Disclaimer

All communication activities and dissemination activities, equipment, materials, etc. (see Grant Agreement, Article 17 for a list of activities) must acknowledge EC funding by displaying

- the European flag (emblem) and
- the funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

Further guidance and flag options are available here:

- [Guide acknowledgment of EU funding](#)
- [Download EU flags](#)

Some INERRANT communication & dissemination templates are made available centrally (e.g., PowerPoint template, Word template) which already abide by the EC’s rules as stated above. These templates are stored in the project management platform and should be used by the partners for the respective project-related activities.

In addition, any communication or dissemination activity must include the following disclaimer:

“Funded by the European Union under grant agreement no 101147457. This report reflects the views only of the authors and does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission can be held responsible or liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.”

5.5 Standards regarding documents prepared in INERRANT

5.5.1 Templates

In general, the partners are asked to use the templates provided for INERRANT. The following templates are or will be made available:

- Deliverables template
- Word template

- PowerPoint template
- Poster template
- Team Leader reporting template
- Work Package Leader reporting template

Further templates can be prepared by the PMO, if necessary.

Documents which are distributed outside of the consortium or final versions of deliverables, agendas and meeting minutes must always be converted into a PDF file.

5.5.2 Naming of documents

Any document produced in INERRANT should be named in the following manner:

- **Deliverables**

INERRANT_101103053_Dx.x_Name_of_Deliverable_vx

INERRANT_101103053_Dx.x_Name_of_Deliverable_final

- **Other documents:**

INERRANT_Name_of_Meeting_Name_of_presentation_acronym

(e.g., INERRANT_Kick-off_Meeting_WP8_MGT_Eurice)

INERRANT_Name_of_Meeting_Name_of_Document

(e.g., INERRANT_Kick-off_Meeting_Minutes_final)

INERRANT_Name_of_Document

(e.g., INERRANT_contacts_list)

5.5.3 Versioning and keeping track

Keeping track of document versions is important. Accordingly, different versions of documents should be clearly distinguishable.

Therefore, if a partner has added comments or has made modifications to a document, it is absolutely necessary that the document is renamed by either:

- Including a new version number; or
- By adding the partner's acronym or person's initials

Adding the partner's acronym or person's initials is preferred for example for modifications to minutes or in the internal review process of a deliverable.

Example:

- First draft of minutes named: INERRANT_Kick-off-Meeting_Minutes_Draft_v0.1
- Partner XX adds comments and renames: INERRANT_Kick-off-Meeting_Minutes_Draft_v0.1_XX

Giving the draft a new version number is recommended for instance if internal feedback is included, but there is another round of internal review.

Example:

- Deliverable draft after first round of internal review is named:
INERRANT_101103053_D8.2_Management_Guide_v0.2

if it is circulated for another round of internal review.

Any modification or adjustment should be clearly visible in the document, i.e., by using the track changes mode or highlighting changes in another way.

Upon approval of the partners concerned, the document should be cleaned from all comments and track changes, and receive its final name (e.g., INERRANT_Kick-off_Meeting_Minutes_final).

6. Conclusion

This Management Guide gives clear guidance for a number of standard workflows and procedures in the INERRANT project.

This is the public version of the Management Guide. The INERRANT partners will receive a more detailed document outlining the procedures and standards mentioned therein. They will be reminded of them by the PMO on a regular basis or if the need arises.

Abiding to certain workflows and standards will make the collaboration in the project easier for all partners as a reliable basis has been established. It will also lead to better quality and early detection of problems and risks and foster the open interaction between all INERRANT partners.

